

Architectural support for Software Performance in Continuous Software Engineering: a Systematic Mapping Study

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Protocol

- Defining research questions
- Conducting search
 - Identification of search strings
 - Identification of bibliographic sources
 - Identification of inclusion/exclusion criteria
 - Search
- Selection process
 - Testing the applicability of inclusion and exclusion criteria
 - Applying inclusion and exclusion criteria to title and abstract
 - Snowballing
 - Full reading
- Data Extraction
 - Definition of coding schema
 - Test coding schema on 10 papers
 - Refinement of the coding schema
 - Data extraction
- Mapping of papers